

Physicochemical studies of some transition metal complexes with acyclic and cyclic monoterpenoids

Anil Kr. Bansal, P. L. Sharma and Meena Nagar*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

Manuscript received 17 June 2003, revised 23 August 2005, accepted 9 September 2005

Abstract : Complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) were synthesized via template reactions. The formation equilibria of binary and ternary complexes with glycine and leucine as primary ligands and terpenoids or 2-cis-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadien-1-ol (CDOA) and 4-allyl-2-methoxy-phenol (L) as secondary ligands have been investigated. The complexes were characterized by usual methods. The binary and the ternary complexes have square planar and octahedral configurations respectively.

Keywords : Transition metal complex, monoterpenoids, photometric studies.

In continuation of our previous works¹ on complexes of terpenoids and their derivatives, we report here in the system complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with 2-cis-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadien-1-ol and 4-allyl-2-methoxy-phenol.

Results and discussion

Potentiometric studies on binary and ternary complexes with secondary ligands (viz. CDOA and L) :

Bjerrum's pH metric titrations were carried out for potentiometric measurements and were considered as Lewis acid base titrations. The lowering in value of pH was due to complex formation in the solution². Figs. 1 and 2, curve D, containing equimolar quantities of metal ions and terpenoid solution (at $\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) showed an inflection at 2 mol of base. The stability of complexes follow Irving and William's order³, the order of stability was found to be Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} for both ligands viz. CDOA and L.

Fig. 1. (○) Gly (A), (□) AMP (B), (Δ) Ni^{III}-Gly (C), (○) Ni^{II}-AMP (D).

Fig. 2. (♦) Gly (A), (□) CDO (B), (Δ) Cu^{II}-Gly (C), (○) Cu^{II}-CDOA (D), (●) Cu^{II}-Gly-CDOA (E).

Potentiometric studies on ternary complexes of transition metal ions :

The potentiometric titration curves (Figs. 1 and 2, curve E) of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} in presence of equimolar solutions of amino acids (glycine and leucine) and secondary ligands (terpenoids) showed an inflection in the graph at 2 mol of base added per mol of metal ions for the ternary systems. The curves for ternary systems lie below the curve for MA and ML₂ binary systems composite curves. Mixed ligand complexes MAL are supposed to exist in the (1 : 1 : 1) M : A : L system (M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}). The stability of ternary complexes was experimentally determined from pH metric titrations are non superimposable with the composite curve drawn by adding the horizontal distance for titration of M(AAH) system and ligand terpenoids alone, suggesting the formation of mixed ligand complexes.

Binary complexes occur comparatively at a high pH, than the initial pH value noted in the titration for the ternary solutions corresponding to mixed complex formation. Thus it is to be reasonable to assume that in the initial stages the formation of a ternary complex involves the simultaneous addition of both the ligands.

Conductometric studies of binary and ternary complexes of transition metal ions :

Composition of complexes formed by the interaction of CDOA and L with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} was determined by reverse conductometric titration by Job's molar ratio method. By plotting a graph between conductance and volume of metal ion added, an inflection in the curve was obtained at the point of complexation. Molar conductance was calculated by measuring the conductance at the complexation point.

Spectrophotometric studies :

The absorbance of the solution containing metal ion and aminoacids in 1 : 1 molar ratio have shown a single maxima over complete visible range of spectrophotometer. Job's continuous variation method was also performed with equimolar solutions of metal salts and amino acids in different proportions at a fixed pH. The absorbance data for these solutions were obtained at a fixed λ_{\max} . In the curve a maxima appeared at X = 0.5, absorption spectra showed the formation of 1 : 2 complex. The position of absorption maxima remain unaltered with the change in the pH but intensity of the peak varied. The absorption of the solutions containing transition metal ions, amino acids and terpenoids in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio at constant pH in presence of 0.1 M KNO₃ at 35 ± 0.5

°C has been studied over the complete range of visible spectra. λ_{\max} has been determined for each ternary system and compared with data for binary complexes.

Spectral studies of binary and ternary complexes of Cu^{II} :

The excitations of molecular vibrations and rotations gives rise to absorption bands in the infrared regions^{4a}. In the spectrum of 2-*cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadien-1-ol (CDOA), a sharp band observed at 1740 cm⁻¹ a weak band at 1657 cm⁻¹ and a medium sharp band is observed at 1640 cm⁻¹ were assigned to aldehyde (-CHO) group^{4b}, π -allylic group and methyl group respectively. In the IR spectra of complex derivatives (L = CDOA) the coordination sites are oxygen and π -allylic bonds^{4c}, when a ligand is coordinated to atleast one additional atom, the atom to which a ligand coordinates is introduced into ligand's vibrating system. This means IR of the coordinated ligand will differ from that of free ligand. IR spectra of binary and ternary complexes of Cu^{II} with CDOA and AA (Gly and Leu) exhibit strong band at 2890-2905, 1682-1704, 1628-1640, 3363-3367, 509-515, 400-410 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν_{as} N-H, ν C=O, ν C=C, ν HOH, ν M-N, ν M-O stretching respectively. The IR of the 4-allyl-2-methoxy-phenol (L) exhibit sharp and strong bands at 3400, 2992, 1250 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν O-H, ν C=C and ν C-O phenolic stretching vibrations respectively. IR of Cu^{II} with L and AA exhibits absorption bands at 1190-1213, 2914-2920 and 2989-2992 cm⁻¹ assigned to phenolic ν C-O, ν_{as} N-H and ν C=C respectively. The lower shifting of phenolic ν C-O stretching vibration indicated the complexation of these groups with metal ion. The

Table 1

Metal complexes	Molar ratio	Conductance at complexation point $l \times 10^3$ mho	Specific conductance $l \times 10^3$ mho/cm	Molar conductance mho/cm ² mol
Cu-CDOA	1 : 1	0.88	0.7937	7.937
Cu-AMP	1 : 1	0.82	0.7396	7.396
Ni-CDOA	1 : 1	0.72	0.6494	6.494
Ni-AMP	1 : 1	0.61	0.5502	5.502
Cu-Gly-CDOA	1 : 1	0.93	0.8389	8.389
Cu-Gly-AMP	1 : 1	0.84	0.7577	7.577
Ni-Gly-CDOA	1 : 1	0.77	0.6945	6.948
Ni-Gly-AMP	1 : 1	0.63	0.5683	5.683
Cu-Leu-CDOA	1 : 1	0.97	0.8749	8.749
Cu-Leu-AMP	1 : 1	0.87	0.7847	7.847
Ni-Leu-CDOA	1 : 1	0.83	0.7487	7.487
Ni-Leu-AMP	1 : 1	0.70	0.6314	6.314

unchanged frequency of $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ indicated that this group is not involved in coordination. The disappearance of $\nu\text{O}-\text{H}$ stretching vibration on complexation showed deprotonation of L ligand.

IR spectra of ternary complexes of glycine and leucine correlation with free ligand revealed that the coordination of ligand to metal ion lead to the following changes in IR frequencies due to disappearance of νNH_3 frequency. New bands corresponding to νNH_2 appeared, $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{COO}$ increased and $\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{COO}$ decreased. These changes suggest the coordination of amino acids bidentate chelating agent. The non superimposability of ternary complexes with binary complexes suggest the formation of ternary complexes. These complexes showed a medium intensity absorption band around $860-870\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to rocking mode of coordinated water molecule and this water molecule showed IR absorption band in the region $3200-3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{O}-\text{H}$ vibrations and at $1500-1510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to its scissoring vibrations. Generally these bands are obscured by ligand bands.

It was further supported by the presence of bands in

the region of $505-535, 400-438\text{ cm}^{-1}$, due to the $\nu\text{Cu}-\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{Cu}-\text{O}$ modes respectively. Magnetic susceptibility measurements provided useful information regarding to the bonding in various types of complexes showed 1.75-1.79 B.M., while ternary complexes showed 1.81-1.94 B.M.

Spectral studies of binary and ternary complexes of Ni^{II} :

IR spectra of nickel complexes with CDOA and AA exhibited absorption bands at 1670-1687, 1600-1621, 1465-1470, 1420, 2775-2782 and 1724-1730 cm^{-1} , respectively assigned to $\nu\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$, νCH_3 , $\nu\text{C}-\text{H}$, $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$, νCOO stretching vibrations respectively. The lower shifting of $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching vibrations indicated that metal is coordinated aldehydic oxygen and π -allylic bond. IR of nickel(II) complexes with L and AA exhibited the bands at 2800-2808, 1184-1208 and 2988-2992 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{N}-\text{H}$, $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ phenolic and $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching vibrations respectively. The lower shifting of $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ frequency indicated that these groups have coordinated to metal ion. The $\nu\text{O}-\text{H}$ frequency disappeared on

Table 2. Synthesis, analysis and physical properties of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with CDOA, AMP and AA (viz. Gly and Leu)

Complex	Primary ligand	Secondary ligand	Molar ratio	Complexes and colour	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Yield (%)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
								C	H	N	S	Cu
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	-	CDOA	1 : 2	[CuCDOA ₂](NO ₃) ₂ Blue	498 (492.1)	65	1.79	48.23 (48.82)	6.48 (6.56)	5.63 (5.70)	-	12.76 (12.96)
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	-	AMP	1 : 2	[Cu(AMP) ₂] Brown	400 (389.9)	72	1.76	60.00 (61.60)	5.54 (5.69)	-	-	15.89 (16.30)
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	Gly	CDOA	1 : 1 : 1	[Cu(CDOA)(Gly)(H ₂ O) ₂] Yellowish blue	394 (387.8)	74	1.95	36.58 (37.16)	6.14 (6.24)	7.11 (7.22)	-	16.13 (16.38)
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	Gly	AMP	1 : 1 : 1	[Cu(AMP)(Gly)(H ₂ O) ₂] Brown	340 (336.8)	73	1.86	42.39 (42.79)	5.63 (5.69)	4.12 (4.16)	-	18.69 (18.87)
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	Leu	CDOA	1 : 1 : 1	[Cu(CDOA)(Leu)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ Blue	450 (443.9)	69	1.97	42.70 (43.28)	7.17 (7.27)	6.23 (6.31)	-	14.12 (14.31)
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	Leu	AMP	1 : 1 : 1	[Cu(AMP)(Leu)(H ₂ O) ₂] Dark brown	400 (392.9)	70	1.88	48.04 (48.90)	6.80 (6.93)	3.50 (3.57)	-	15.88 (16.77)
Ni(NO ₃) ₂	-	CDOA	1 : 2	[Ni(CDOA) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ Green	490 (487.1)	63	Dia.	49.02 (49.31)	6.58 (6.61)	5.72 (5.75)	-	11.98 (12.05)
Ni(NO ₃) ₂	-	AMP	1 : 2	[Ni(AMP) ₂] Dark green	390 (385.1)	71	Dia.	61.59 (62.38)	5.69 (5.76)	-	-	15.05 (15.24)
Ni(NO ₃) ₂	Gly	CDOA	1 : 1 : 1	[Ni(CDOA)(Gly)(H ₂ O) ₂] Greenish black	390 (383.1)	66	3.21	36.95 (37.63)	6.20 (6.32)	7.18 (7.32)	-	15.05 (15.32)
Ni(NO ₃) ₂	Gly	AMP	1 : 1 : 1	[Ni(AMP)(Gly)(H ₂ O) ₂] Yellowish green	345 (337.9)	61	3.17	41.77 (43.41)	5.55 (5.77)	4.06 (4.22)	-	17.01 (17.68)
Ni(NO ₃) ₂	Leu	CDOA	1 : 1 : 1	[Ni(CDOA)(Leu)(H ₂ O) ₂] Green	445 (439.1)	60	3.28	43.18 (43.76)	7.25 (7.35)	6.30 (6.38)	-	13.19 (13.37)
Ni(NO ₃) ₂	Leu	AMP	1 : 1 : 1	[Ni(AMP)(Leu)(H ₂ O) ₂] Dark green	392 (388.8)	66	3.23	49.02 (49.52)	6.94 (7.01)	3.57 (3.61)	6.16 (6.26)	14.97 (15.12)

complexation. The broad band in the region 3000–2500 cm^{-1} are present in the spectra of glycine and leucine which disappeared on complexation. The broad absorption in the region 3363–3470 cm^{-1} have been assigned to ν_{as} O–H stretching vibration of coordinated molecule. The δ H–O–H manifest as the shoulder in the region 1615–1630 cm^{-1} in the spectra of ternary complexes. The band at 850–865 cm^{-1} was assigned to rocking mode of coordinated water molecule¹⁴. It was further supported by the presence of the band in the region 515–532, 410–440 cm^{-1} due to ν Ni–N, and Ni–O modes respectively.

Elemental analysis and magnetic susceptibility suggests that all binary complexes and ternary complexes have square planar and octahedral geometry respectively. All results are reported in Table 2.

Biocidal assay :

The antibacterial and antifungal activities of the ligand and their metal complexes have been evaluated by testing these compounds against bacteria (*viz. Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*) and fungi (*viz. Alternaria alternata* and *Aspergillus niger*) at different concentrations by using paper disc method and spore germination technique respectively⁶. In all ligands bactericidal and fungicidal activity increased as the concentration increased. The enhanced activity of newly synthesized complex derivatives can be explained on the basis of chelation theory⁷ the variation in effectiveness of different complexes against different organism depends either on the permeability of the cells of microbes or differences of ribosomes of microbial cells⁸ fungicidal screening data revealed that at low concentration the inhibition of sporulation is less as compared to higher concentration or in other words, all the metal chelates had significant fungitoxicity at 1000 ppm.

All the pyrex glasses were used for the chemotherapeutic studies. The cleaned glasswares were placed in an autoclave for sterilization at 121 °C for half an hour under 15 lbs pressure.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The pH measurement were carried out on Elicomodel digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) equipped with a combined glass and calomel electrodes. The instrument has been calibrated at pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2 using buffer solutions. The accuracy of data obtained during the pH measurements was ensured by calibrating the pH meter at 35 \pm

0.5 °C in different regions of pH below 3.5 and above 10.1 respectively. Conductance studies were carried out on Toshniwal conductivity bridge with a dip type cell. Spectrophotometric studies were carried out with the help of Systronic UV-VIS spectrophotometer in the visible range (300–800 nm) using quartz cells of 1 cm path length at 35 \pm 0.5 °C. A tungsten filament lamp was employed as the light source. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer by KBr technique and elemental analysis on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were however recorded on Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant.

Preparation of binary complexes :

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The following general procedure was adopted for synthesis of the copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes with respective ligands (*viz.* CDOA and L) in 25 ml dry ethanol in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for a pe-

Table 3. Bacteriocidal screening data

Comps.	Inhibition zone and activity index	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (+ve)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (-ve)
CDOA	0.55 (0.78)	0.50 (0.71)
Cu-CDOA	0.76 (1.08)	0.66 (0.94)
Cu-Gly-CDOA	0.90 (1.20)	0.85 (1.14)
Ni-Leu-CDOA	0.86 (1.23)	0.75 (1.07)
Ni-CDOA	1.18 (1.68)	1.10 (1.57)
Ni-Gly-CDOA	1.33 (1.90)	1.25 (1.78)
Ni-Leu-CDOA	1.28 (1.83)	1.20 (1.71)
AMP	0.84 (1.20)	0.75 (1.07)
Cu-AMP	1.04 (1.48)	0.96 (1.37)
Cu-Gly-AMP	1.30 (1.86)	1.20 (1.71)
Cu-Leu-AMP	1.25 (1.78)	1.12 (1.60)
Ni-AMP	1.39 (1.98)	1.25 (1.78)
Ni-Gly-AMP	1.70 (2.43)	1.60 (2.28)
Ni-Leu-AMP	1.60 (2.28)	1.50 (2.14)

Table 4. Fungicidal screening data
Average % inhibition of spore germination after 72 h

Compds.	<i>Alternaria alternata</i> (conc. in ppm)			<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (conc. in ppm)		
	100	500	1000	100	500	1000
CDOA	27	39	56	25	40	56
Cu-CDOA	40	56	76	39	58	73
Cu-Gly-CDOA	50	66	81	49	67	84
Cu-Leu-CDOA	48	65	79	47	66	82
Ni-CDOA	42	62	78	40	61	75
Ni-Gly-CDOA	52	75	88	53	69	83
Ni-Leu-CDOA	50	72	87	49	67	80
AMP	37	45	63	56	43	63
Cu-AMP	45	58	70	47	61	78
Cu-Gly-AMP	54	66	77	56	69	86
Cu-Leu-AMP	50	64	75	52	67	84
Ni-AMP	49	64	79	47	64	81
Ni-Gly-AMP	56	71	87	54	71	89
Ni-Leu-AMP	55	70	85	52	70	87

riod of 3–4 h. Special characteristic feature for isolation of Cu-CDOA complex was 7 h refluxing required for noodle shaped crystal formation. After the completion of reaction. the complex so formed was filtered and washed with ethanol, later with ether and dried.

Preparation of ternary complexes :

The following general procedure was adopted for synthesis of the copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes with

CDOA and L and amino acids (viz. Gly and Leu) in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio. A weighted amount of copper nitrate dissolved in double distilled ethanol was added to a solution containing respective primary ligands (viz. Gly and Leu) and respective secondary ligands (viz. CDOA and L) dissolved in ethanol and the contents were refluxed for about 3 h. The complex separated out was filtered and washed with ethanol and dried under vacuum.

References

1. M. Chand, P. Lata and Meena Nagar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 861.
2. A. E. Martell and S. Charbek, "Organic Sesquiterpenic Agent", John Willey and Sons Inc., New York, 1959; M. Schnitzer and S. I. M. Skinner. *Soil Sci.*, 1963, **96**, 86.
3. H. M. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192; *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746.
4. (a) S. F. A. Kettle, "Coordination Compounds", Thomas Nelson and Sons Ltd., 1969, 51; (b) N. Koji, "Infrared Spectroscopy", Nankodo Co. Ltd., 1962, 91; (c) W. U. Malik, G. D. Tuli and R. D. Madan, "Selected Topics in Inorganic Chemistry": S. Chand and Co., 1976, 36.
5. A. Mishra, M. P. Singh and J. P. Singh. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 249.
6. M. C. Bryant, "Antibiotic and their Laboratory Control". Butterworth, London, 1988, 20; A. Bawer, W. M. M. Kirby, J. C. Sherris and M. Truck, *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.*, 1966, **45**, 493.
7. W. H. R. Shaw, *Nature (London)*, 1961, **192**, 754.
8. S. K. Sengupta, D. P. Pandey, B. K. Srivastava and V. K. Sharma, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 349.